

Secrecy capacity analysis of bi-static backscatter communication systems

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ABSTRACT

The rapid adoption of battery-free internet-of-things (IoT) sensors in multiple environments ranging from agriculture to wildlife surveillance, has seen increased research interest in backscatter communication (BSC) technology. BSC is viewed as a potential technology to enable the further spread of sustainable battery-free IoT applications in environments and scenarios where bulkier-sized battery-powered IoT devices would be unsuitable. In this study, we investigate the secrecy capacity of a bi-static BSC network in the presence of a malicious eavesdropper. The proposed BSC system consists of a reader, multiple backscatter devices, and an eavesdropper. We derive closed-form strictly positive secrecy capacity (SPSC) expressions and ergodic secrecy capacity (ESC) expressions for the BSC reader. Monte Carlo simulations verify the exact capacity expressions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid adoption and proliferation of internet-of-things (IoT) in scenarios and environments ranging from infrastructure monitoring (such as bridges, roads, and pipelines) to implanted health-care monitoring, has driven backscatter communication (BSC) research [1]. BSC devices enable the design and deployment of sustainable ultra-low-power IoT solutions into scenarios unsuitable for bulkier battery-powered IoT devices such as inside the human body for healthcare monitoring [2]. Research by Jang *et al.* [3] define a backscatter tag as a device that reflects nearby transmitter excitation signals and then selectively amplifies, or modifies the phase, and/or frequency of the signal for modulation. A nearby receiver captures the backscattered signal and extracts the information injected by the tag. There are three types of BSC architectures, which are [2]-[4]: i) monostatic: the reader utilizes the same antenna as an emitter and receiver, to receive signals from the backscatter sensors; ii) Bi-static: here, the transmitter and receiver are not located on the same device. But are separated apart geographically. This architecture is suitable for long-range transmissions; iii) ambient: the transmitter scatters radio frequency (RF) signals over a short-range and the reader receives and decodes the backscattered signals from the tags [5]-[8].

The monostatic model is the cheapest of the three to design since they require fewer antenna elements, however, in this paper, we prefer the bi-static model to explain in the consistently following section. Various recent works have focused on secure communications for BSC. In [9]-[12] proposed a

physical layer security (PLS) solution over an alternative to application layer security by cryptography. As cryptography is computationally complex for existing radio frequency identification (RFID) systems. Which are also another example of BSC systems. The authors obtained asymptotic closed-form secrecy outage probability (SOP) expressions for their proposed system operating in correlated Rayleigh fading conditions. Song *et al.* [13], studied PLS with artificial noise (AN) utilized to decrease the signal-to-noise interference noise (SINR) of the eavesdropper. PLS was investigated for ambient BSC systems with multiple tags, the authors derived exact detection rates for the eavesdropper and the reader [14], [15]. Motivated by these recent ideas in securing BSC systems, we add the following contributions to the growing field of BSC security: we derive exact strictly positive secrecy capacity (SPSC) expressions as well as ergodic secrecy capacity expressions (ESC) for the backscatter communication reader with channel gain following Rayleigh distribution and we also present performance curves demonstrating the improvement of secrecy capacity at the reader. All closed-form expressions are verified by Monte Carlo simulations.

The remainder of this paper is as follows. In section 2, we describe the bi-static backscatter communication system located in the vicinity of an eavesdropper. Then, section 3 describes our closed-form equations SPSC expressions. In section 4, we derive the ESC expressions, followed by a discussion of our findings in section 5 and a summary in section 6.

2. BI-STATIC BACKSCATTER COMMUNICATION SYSTEM MODEL

In this study, we evaluate the secrecy capacity performance of a multiple backscatter devices (BDs) system, which consists of a reader, K BDs, and a nearby located eavesdropper, as illustrative in Figure 1. We define p_k , q_k and g_k as the channel gains from the transmitter antenna at the reader to the k -th BD, the k -th BD to the receive antenna at the reader, and the k -th BD to the eavesdropper, respectively. We assume that all the channel gains over Rayleigh fading distribution [11], i.e., $p_k \sim CN(0, \lambda_p)$, $q_k \sim CN(0, \lambda_q)$, and $g_k \sim CN(0, \lambda_g)$.

Figure 1. Insecure bi-static backscatter communication

As multiple BDs form a group, the best BD is selected before transmitting. The BD selection strategy is expressed as [3]:

$$k^* = \arg \max_{0 \leq k \leq K} |\bar{Z}_k|^2, \bar{Z} \in \{p, q, g\}. \quad (1)$$

The received signal at the reader from the k -th BD is written as [12]:

$$\bar{y}_{R_k} = \sqrt{P_S} p_k q_k s x + \bar{\omega}_k, \quad (2)$$

where P_S is the reader transmitter power, s is the reader query signal, x is the BD information signal, and $\bar{\omega}_k$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) in which $\bar{\omega}_k \sim CN(0, N_0)$. Due to the architecture of the backscatter system [16], p_k and q_k are correlated. On the other hand, in the bi-static system, p_k , and q_k channels are considered partially interested [17]. In reality, bi-static architecture is preferred to the monostatic system. Therefore, in this paper, we assume the proposed system is bi-static. In another case, at the eavesdropper, we calculate the intercepted signal from the k -th BD can be written as:

$$\bar{y}_{E_k} = \sqrt{P_E} p_k g_k s x + \bar{\omega}_{E_k}, \quad (3)$$

where P_E is the transmit power of the eavesdropper, g_k denotes the channels gain from the BD to the eavesdropper, $\bar{\omega}_{E_k}$ and is the AWGN at eavesdropper with $\bar{\omega}_{E_k} \sim CN(0, N_0)$. From (1)-(3), we calculate the received instantaneous signal-to-noise-ratios (SNRs) at the reader and the eavesdropper as:

$$\bar{\gamma}_{R_{k^*}} \triangleq \frac{P_S |p_{k^*}|^2 |q_{k^*}|^2}{N_0} = \rho_S |p_{k^*}|^2 |q_{k^*}|^2, \tag{4}$$

$$\bar{\gamma}_{E_{k^*}} \triangleq \frac{P_E |p_{k^*}|^2 |g_{k^*}|^2}{N_0} = \rho_E |p_{k^*}|^2 |g_{k^*}|^2, \tag{5}$$

where $\rho_S = \frac{P_S}{N_0}$ and $\rho_E = \frac{P_E}{N_0}$ are the transmit SNR. We can see, from (4) and (5), the channel capacity of the reader and capacity of the eavesdropper's channels can be present as:

$$C_{R_{k^*}} = \log_2 (1 + \bar{\gamma}_{R_{k^*}}), \tag{6}$$

and

$$C_{E_{k^*}} = \log_2 (1 + \bar{\gamma}_{E_{k^*}}) \tag{7}$$

Using (6) and (7), we can express the immediate secrecy capacity of the reader system as [18]:

$$\bar{C}_S = \left[C_{R_{k^*}} - C_{E_{k^*}} \right]^+ = \begin{cases} \left[\log_2 \left(\frac{1 + \bar{\gamma}_{R_{k^*}}}{1 + \bar{\gamma}_{E_{k^*}}} \right) \right]^+, & \text{if } \bar{\gamma}_{R_{k^*}} \geq \bar{\gamma}_{E_{k^*}} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \tag{8}$$

where $[x]^+ = \max(x, 0)$.

3. STRICTLY POSITIVE SECRECY CAPACITY ANALYSIS

3.1. The channel models

Let us start with the Rayleigh fading channel, the probability-density-functions (PDF) and cumulative-distribution-functions (CDF) of p, q, and g are given by [19].

$$f_{|p|^2}(x) = \frac{1}{\lambda_p} e^{-\frac{x}{\lambda_p}}, \tag{9}$$

$$f_{|q|^2}(y) = \frac{1}{\lambda_q} e^{-\frac{y}{\lambda_q}}, \tag{10}$$

$$f_{|g|^2}(z) = \frac{1}{\lambda_g} e^{-\frac{z}{\lambda_g}}, \tag{11}$$

and

$$F_{|p|^2}(x) = 1 - e^{-\frac{x}{\lambda_p}}, \tag{12}$$

$$F_{|q|^2}(y) = 1 - e^{-\frac{y}{\lambda_q}}, \tag{13}$$

$$F_{|g|^2}(z) = 1 - e^{-\frac{z}{\lambda_g}}, \tag{14}$$

further, we have random variables (RVs) $f_{|\bar{z}_{k^*}|^2}(x)$ as exponential distributions which $\bar{Z} \in \{p, q, g\}$, are then $f_{|\bar{z}_{k^*}|^2}(x)$ to presented following [20]:

$$f_{|\bar{z}_{k^*}|^2} = \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{k\gamma(K,k)}{\lambda_Z} e^{-\frac{k}{\lambda_Z}x}, \tag{15}$$

where $\Upsilon(K, k) = \frac{(-1)^{k-1}K!}{k!(K-k)!}$.

3.2. SPSC of reader

From (6)-(8), the SPSC for decode and forward (DF) case can be expressed as [21]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S &= \Pr(\bar{C}_S > 0) = \Pr\left(\log_2\left(\frac{1 + \bar{\gamma}_{R_k^*}}{1 + \bar{\gamma}_{E_k^*}}\right) > 0\right) = \Pr\left(\bar{\gamma}_{R_k^*} > \bar{\gamma}_{E_k^*}\right) \\
 &= \Pr\left(|p_{k^*}|^2 |q_{k^*}|^2 > \frac{\rho_E}{\rho_S} |p_{k^*}|^2 |g_{k^*}|^2\right) = \Pr\left(|q_{k^*}|^2 > \frac{\rho_E}{\rho_S} |g_{k^*}|^2\right) = \int_0^{+\infty} f_{|g_{k^*}|^2}(x) \int_{\frac{\rho_E x}{\rho_S}}^{+\infty} f_{|q_{k^*}|^2}(y) dx dy.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{16}$$

Proposition 1: the closed-form expression of SPSC to the reader is written as:

$$S = \sum_{k_2=1}^K \sum_{k_3=1}^K \frac{k_2 \rho_S \lambda_q \Upsilon(K, k_2) \Upsilon(K, k_3)}{(k_2 \rho_S \lambda_q + k_3 \rho_E \lambda_g)}. \tag{17}$$

Proof 1: from (16) we use PDF of (15), S is expanded as (18):

$$\begin{aligned}
 S &= \int_0^{+\infty} f_{|g_{k^*}|^2}(x) \int_{\frac{\rho_E x}{\rho_S}}^{+\infty} f_{|q_{k^*}|^2}(y) dx dy = \sum_{k_2=1}^K \sum_{k_3=1}^K \frac{k_2 k_3 \Upsilon(K, k_2) \Upsilon(K, k_3)}{\lambda_g \lambda_q} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{k_2 x}{\lambda_g}} \int_{\frac{\rho_E x}{\rho_S}}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{k_3 y}{\lambda_q}} dx dy \\
 &= \sum_{k_2=1}^K \sum_{k_3=1}^K \frac{k_2 \Upsilon(K, k_2) \Upsilon(K, k_3)}{\lambda_g} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-x\left(\frac{k_2}{\lambda_g} + \frac{\rho_E k_3}{\rho_S \lambda_q}\right)} dx.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{18}$$

finally, we have SPSC of the system as shown in:

$$S = \sum_{k_2=1}^K \sum_{k_3=1}^K \frac{k_2 \rho_S \lambda_q \Upsilon(K, k_2) \Upsilon(K, k_3)}{(k_2 \rho_S \lambda_q + k_3 \rho_E \lambda_g)}. \tag{19}$$

based on the aforementioned results, *Proof 1* is complete.

4. ERGODIC SECRECY CAPACITY ANALYSIS

The exact closed-form expressions for ESC are derived by [22], (4).

$$\bar{C}_S = \left[\underbrace{\{C_{R_{k^*}}\}}_{A_1} - \underbrace{\{C_{E_{k^*}}\}}_{A_2} \right]^+, \tag{20}$$

where $\{\bullet\}$ denotes expectation operation.

Proposition 2: the closed-form expression of ESC to the reader is written by:

$$\bar{C}_S = \left[\sum_{k_1=1}^K \sum_{k_2=1}^K \frac{\Upsilon(K, k_1) \Upsilon(K, k_2)}{\ln 2} G_{1,3}^{3,1} \left(\frac{k_2 k_1}{\rho_S \lambda_p \lambda_o} \middle| \begin{matrix} 0 \\ 0, 1, 0 \end{matrix} \right) - \sum_{k_3=1}^K \sum_{k_4=1}^K \frac{\Upsilon(K, k_3) \Upsilon(K, k_4)}{\ln 2} n \times G_{1,3}^{3,1} \left(\frac{k_3 k_4}{\rho_E \lambda_p \lambda_g} \middle| \begin{matrix} 0 \\ 0, 1, 0 \end{matrix} \right) \right]^+ \tag{21}$$

Proof 2: first, we can calculate A_1 as follows:

$$A_1 = \{C_{R_{k^*}}\} = \left\{ \log_2 \left(1 + \bar{\gamma}_{R_{k^*}} \right) \right\} = \left\{ \log_2 \left(1 + \rho_S |p_{k^*}|^2 |q_{k^*}|^2 \right) \right\} = \frac{1}{\ln 2} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{1+x} \left[1 - F_{|p_{k^*}|^2 |q_{k^*}|^2} \left(\frac{x}{\rho_S} \right) \right] dx. \tag{22}$$

we have $F_{|p_{k^*}|^2 |q_{k^*}|^2}(x)$ is calculated as:

$$F_{|p_{k^*}|^2 |q_{k^*}|^2} \left(\frac{x}{\rho_S} \right) = Pr \left(|p_{k^*}|^2 < \frac{x}{|q_{k^*}|^2 \rho_S} \right) = \int_0^{+\infty} f_{|q_{k^*}|^2}(y) \int_0^{\frac{x}{\rho_S y}} f_{|p_{k^*}|^2}(z) dy dz$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{k_1=1}^K \sum_{k_2=1}^K Y(K, k_1) Y(K, k_2) \frac{k_1 k_2}{\lambda_q \lambda_p} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{k_1}{\lambda_q} y} \int_0^{\frac{x}{\rho_S y}} e^{-\frac{k_2}{\lambda_p} z} dy dz \\
 &= \sum_{k_1=1}^K \sum_{k_2=1}^K Y(K, k_1) Y(K, k_2) \frac{k_1}{\lambda_q} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{k_1}{\lambda_q} y} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{k_2 x}{\rho_S \lambda_p y}} \right) dy \\
 &= \sum_{k_1=1}^K \sum_{k_2=1}^K Y(K, k_1) Y(K, k_2) \left(\frac{k_1}{\lambda_q} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{k_1}{\lambda_q} y} - \frac{k_1}{\lambda_q} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{k_1}{\lambda_q} y} e^{-\frac{k_2 x}{\rho_S \lambda_p y}} dy \right) \\
 &= \sum_{k_1=1}^K \sum_{k_2=1}^K Y(K, k_1) Y(K, k_2) \left(1 - \frac{k_1}{\lambda_q} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{k_1 y}{\lambda_q} - \frac{k_2 x}{\rho_S \lambda_p y}} dy \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

using [23], (3.324.1), $F_{|p_{k^*}|^2 | q_{k^*}|^2}(x)$ as shown in:

$$F_{|p_{k^*}|^2 | q_{k^*}|^2}(x) = \left[1 - \sum_{k_1=1}^K \sum_{k_2=1}^K Y(K, k_1) Y(K, k_2) \times 2 \sqrt{\frac{k_2 k_1 x}{\rho_S \lambda_p \lambda_q}} K_1 \left(2 \sqrt{\frac{k_2 k_1 x}{\rho_S \lambda_p \lambda_q}} \right) \right] \tag{24}$$

Putting (19) into (17) A_1 as shown in:

$$A_1 = \sum_{k_1=1}^K \sum_{k_2=1}^K \frac{Y(K, k_1) Y(K, k_2)}{\ln 2} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{1+x} 2 \sqrt{\frac{k_2 k_1 x}{\rho_S \lambda_p \lambda_q}} K_1 \left(2 \sqrt{\frac{k_2 k_1 x}{\rho_S \lambda_p \lambda_q}} \right) dx \tag{25}$$

in doing so, we make use of the equalities [23], [24], (9.34.3) as:

$$\frac{1}{1+x} = G_{1,1}^{1,1}(x|0), \tag{26}$$

and

$$2 \sqrt{\frac{k_2 k_1 x}{\rho_S \lambda_p \lambda_q}} K_1 \left(2 \sqrt{\frac{k_2 k_1 x}{\rho_S \lambda_p \lambda_q}} \right) = G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left(\frac{k_2 k_1 x}{\rho_S \lambda_p \lambda_q} \middle| 1, 0 \right) \tag{27}$$

Submitting (27) and (26) into (25), A_1 as shown in:

$$A_1 = \sum_{k_1=1}^K \sum_{k_2=1}^K \frac{Y(K, k_1) Y(K, k_2)}{\ln 2} \int_0^{+\infty} G_{1,1}^{1,1}(x|0) G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left(\frac{k_2 k_1 x}{\rho_S \lambda_p \lambda_q} \middle| 1, 0 \right) dx \tag{28}$$

with the help of the [23], (7.811.1), A_1 is calculated as:

$$A_1 = \sum_{k_1=1}^K \sum_{k_2=1}^K \frac{Y(K, k_1) Y(K, k_2)}{\ln 2} G_{1,3}^{3,1} \left(\frac{k_2 k_1}{\rho_S \lambda_p \lambda_q} \middle| 0, 1, 0 \right) \tag{29}$$

similarly, by solving A_1 , A_2 can be obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_2 &= E \left\{ C_{E_{k^*}} \right\} = E \left\{ \log_2 \left(1 + \bar{\gamma}_{E_{k^*}} \right) \right\} = E \left\{ \log_2 \left(1 + \rho_E |p_{k^*}|^2 |g_{k^*}|^2 \right) \right\} \\
 &= \frac{1}{\ln 2} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{1+x} \left[1 - F_{|p_{k^*}|^2 |g_{k^*}|^2} \left(\frac{x}{\rho_E} \right) \right] dx = \sum_{k_3=1}^K \sum_{k_4=1}^K \frac{Y(K, k_3) Y(K, k_4)}{\ln 2} G_{1,3}^{3,1} \left(\frac{k_2 k_1}{\rho_E \lambda_p \lambda_g} \middle| 0, 1, 0 \right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

finally, by substituting (30) and (29) into (20) we can obtain (21).

Proof 2 is completed.

5. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we set the channel gains $\lambda_p = d_p^{-\frac{\beta}{2}}$, $\lambda_q = d_q^{-\frac{\beta}{2}}$, and $\lambda_g = d_g^{-\frac{\beta}{2}}$ which β is the path loss exponent. Monte-Carlo results average over 10^7 independent sample space trials. Especially, the main parameters can be seen in Table 1. Figure 2 plots the curves between SPSC and transmit SNR, with different

values of K . In (17) is used to plot the analytical lines. From Figure 2, we notice that the reader experiences different secrecy capacity performances. In the case of varying the number of distributed backscatter devices, the performance of the $k=6$ line has better compared to the others in the lower SNR region. In the case of varying the number of distributed backscatter devices, the $K = 6$ line has the best performance compared to the others in the lower SNR region. Both lines approach the ceiling $\rho_S = 20 \text{ dB}$, meaning that no performance improvements can be achieved with a greater number of K devices. We can see the analytical curves match well with Monte-Carlo simulations. In Figure 3, we observe the curves between SPSC and transmit SNR, with different values ρ_E . From Figure 3, we notice that the reader experiences different secrecy capacity performances with different values of eavesdropper SNR. Both lines approach the ceiling $\rho_S = 20 \text{ dB}$.

From Figure 4, consider the curves between ESC and transmit SNR, with different values K . In (21) is used to plot the analytical lines. Here, we observe that the reader experiences different ergodic secrecy capacity performances with different values of K distributed backscatter devices. The best performance is achieved when there are many backscatter devices. In Figure 5, corresponding observes between ESC and transmit SNR, with different values ρ_E . Here, we see that the reader experiences different ergodic secrecy capacity performance with different numbers of K distributed backscatter devices. The best performance is achieved when the eavesdropper SNR ρ_E has the lowest value. Finally, in Figure 6, we can see the relationship between ESC and K , different values ρ_E . Here, we see that the reader experiences significant performance gaps with different values of eavesdropper SNR ρ_E . The best performance is achieved when the eavesdropper SNR $\rho_E = 0 \text{ dB}$.

Table 1. Simulation parameters [25]

Parameters	Values	Parameters	Values
K	2	ρ_E	15 dB
β	2	d_p	2 m
d_q	2 m	d_g	2 m

Figure 2. Strictly positive secrecy capacity versus ρ_S in dB varying K

Figure 3. Strictly positive secrecy capacity versus ρ_S in dB varying ρ_E

Figure 4. Ergodic secrecy capacity versus ρ_S in dB varying K

Figure 5. Ergodic secrecy capacity versus ρ_S in dB varying ρ_E

Figure 6. Ergodic secrecy capacity versus K varying ρ_E

6. CONCLUSION

In this study, we provided the secrecy capacity analysis of a bi-static backscatter communication system located in the vicinity of an eavesdropper. We derived exact expressions of the strictly positive and ergodic secrecy capacity of the backscatter reader device. The number of distributed backscatter devices contributes significantly to the ESC of the reader but has no significant impact on the strictly positive secrecy capacity performance. In future work, we will consider the impact of non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) on the secrecy capacity of the system.

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